

MADANIYATLARARO MULOQOTDA EVFEMIZMLARNING KOMMUNIKATIV STRATEGIYA SIFATIDAGI O'RNI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola madaniyatlararo muloqotda evfemizmlarning kommunikativ strategiya sifatidagi o'rnini tahlil qiladi. Evfemizmlar til orqali ijtimoiy noqulayliklarni yumshatish, madaniy tafovutlarni hisobga olgan holda muloqotni muvozanatlash va ijtimoiy keskinliklarni oldini olishga xizmat qiladi. Maqolada evfemizmlar, o'zaro tushunishni ta'minlash va ijtimoiy etikani saqlashda qanday kommunikativ vosita sifatida ishlatilishini, xususan, madaniyatlararo kontekstda qanday qo'llanishini yoritib beriladi. Shu bilan birga, ommaviy axborot vositalaridagi evfemizmlarning roliga ham alohida e'tibor qaratiladi. Evfemizmlar til va madaniyatlar o'rtasida madaniy ko'priq sifatida xizmat qilib, tilning pragmatik va ijtimoiy darajasida muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: evfemizm, madaniyatlararo muloqot, kommunikativ strategiya, til, ijtimoiy muvozanat, ommaviy axborot vositalari, madaniy kompetensiya, pragmatika, diplomatiya, translyatsiya.

Аннотация. В данной статье анализируется роль эвфемизмов как коммуникативной стратегии в межкультурной коммуникации. Эвфемизмы служат средством сглаживания социальных неловкостей через язык, способствуют сбалансированной коммуникации с учётом культурных различий и помогают предотвращать социальную напряжённость. В статье рассматриваются функции эвфемизмов как инструмента общения, обеспечивающего взаимопонимание и соблюдение этических норм, особенно в межкультурной среде. Особое внимание уделяется также роли эвфемизмов в средствах массовой информации. Являясь культурным мостом между языком и культурой, эвфемизмы обладают значительной ценностью как на прагматическом, так и на социальном уровнях языка.

Ключевые слова: эвфемизм, межкультурная коммуникация, коммуникативная стратегия, язык, социальное равновесие, средства массовой информации, культурная компетентность, прагматика, дипломатия, перевод.

Abstract. This article analyzes the role of euphemisms as a communicative strategy in intercultural communication. Euphemisms serve to mitigate social discomforts through language, balance communication with consideration of cultural differences, and help prevent social tensions. The article explores how euphemisms function as a communicative tool to ensure mutual understanding and maintain social ethics, particularly in intercultural contexts. Special attention is also given to the role of euphemisms in mass media. Acting as a cultural bridge between language and culture, euphemisms hold significant value at both the pragmatic and social levels of language.

Keywords: euphemism, intercultural communication, communicative strategy, language, social balance, mass media, cultural competence, pragmatics, diplomacy, translation.

Language serves not only as a medium for exchanging information but also as an expression of social relations, values, and moral norms in intercultural communication. In such

interactions, euphemisms stand out as an important communicative strategy. They typically soften problematic, sensitive, or socially uncomfortable content, thereby helping to balance relationships among interlocutors. In intercultural communication, such expressions are essential in preventing conflicts and addressing cultural differences. This article examines the communicative functions of euphemisms and their use in social and cultural contexts. Language is a direct expression of human thought and social consciousness, performing different functions throughout each stage of human history. Especially in intercultural communication, language is not only a tool for information exchange but also a reflection of social relations, values, mentality, and moral norms. In this process, euphemisms serve as a crucial communicative strategy. They help to deliver content considered sensitive, problematic, or socially inappropriate in a softened manner. Euphemisms generate expressions that match the cultural context and maintain equilibrium between communication participants. One of their primary functions is to prevent or soften potentially conflict-laden situations. In intercultural interactions, this role becomes even more significant. Each culture may have distinct topics considered socially uncomfortable. For instance, while the topic of death may be taboo in one society, it might be openly discussed in another. In such cases, euphemisms are viewed as tools for maintaining social balance by addressing cultural differences among language users.

Mass media is a powerful tool of communication, playing a critical role in shaping public opinion. The linguistic choices made in information dissemination directly influence the effectiveness of this process. This is particularly relevant in intercultural communication contexts. In tense and conflict-prone situations like the political climate in the South Caucasus, the language policies of international media deserve special attention. In such circumstances, euphemisms are chosen as an effective communicative strategy to maintain information neutrality and avoid indirect support of any conflicting parties. By replacing emotionally charged words with neutral or emotionally softened expressions, social tension can be avoided.[1] Delivering information in an indirect and non-positioned manner allows the media to preserve its impartial and objective image. This approach also demonstrates the role of euphemisms as instruments of peacekeeping and communication balancing in intercultural dialogue.

Convenience and mutual understanding can be considered fundamental in verbal communication, including in interethnic interactions. Euphemisms play an essential role in creating a positive emotional environment, as they involve the intentional use of expressions aimed at emotional impact and replacing unfamiliar or harsh language. *Euphemisms include those words and expressions that replace content potentially awkward, sensitive, or impolite for the speaker, with the goal of not offending or upsetting the listener.*[2] Furthermore, word choice is sometimes made not only to serve the listener's comfort but also to obscure or deliberately misrepresent the subject, leading to partial deception or conceptual substitution. The ability to create and use euphemisms must be accompanied by the ability to recognize them in context—something that is not always feasible due to translation challenges in intercultural communication. Specifically, I. N. Nikitina notes that *euphemisms are often not covered in foreign language curricula or in translation theory and practice.*[3] As a result, translators may not detect the euphemistic meaning and instead interpret the expression literally.

Euphemisms function on the pragmatic level of language, where their communicative purpose outweighs their semantic content. From a pragmatic perspective, euphemistic expressions are closely tied to the speaker's intent, the listener's emotional state, social status, and the needs of the communicative context. In this sense, the use of euphemisms in intercultural communication should be considered part of cultural competence.[4] Through euphemisms,

information is conveyed indirectly, in a socially acceptable form. Their communicative function lies in enabling interaction that considers social sensitivity, cultural caution, and norms of etiquette. This is especially relevant in intercultural communication, as participants may possess differing cultural codes, values, and speech norms.

Culturally sensitive topics include sexuality, death, health, disability, financial status, racial or ethnic differences, political beliefs, and religious views. Euphemisms act as intermediaries in bringing such themes into conversation. Their semantically softened and emotionally neutral nature helps maintain emotional stability between speakers. Thus, euphemisms serve as a pragmatic tool for achieving social consensus and avoiding potential misunderstandings or disruptions in social harmony.[5] Their use in intercultural communication is particularly vital in areas such as international diplomacy, business negotiations, tourism, education, social media, and mass communication. For instance, individuals participating in international conferences or formal meetings must convey their ideas with cultural sensitivity, a goal often achieved through euphemistic tools. As a result, language becomes not only a medium of information but also a builder of cultural bridges.

Through euphemisms, communication participants can express respect, caution, and tolerance toward one another. In an intercultural context, this directly affects the quality and effectiveness of social interaction. Linguists suggest studying euphemisms not only as linguistic phenomena but also as tools of socio-cultural communication. *This necessitates the analysis of euphemisms on semantic, pragmatic, and cultural levels.*[6] Euphemisms appear not only in spoken but also in written communication. Their stylistic application is evident in mass media, advertisements, political speeches, and diplomatic documents, where they can directly influence public consciousness. Euphemisms reflect societal stereotypes, taboos, and moral norms, revealing the complex interplay between language and society. This underscores the importance of studying euphemisms as a cultural phenomenon.

The selection and use of euphemistic expressions in communication directly depend on the cultural competence of the speakers involved. Such competence includes not only language proficiency but also intercultural sensitivity, normative reasoning, and sociolinguistic awareness. Therefore, language education programs should incorporate work with euphemistic expressions, explain their role in cultural contexts, and teach proper usage to enable effective intercultural communication. The types and forms of euphemisms vary depending on the cultural environment. While some societies use euphemisms extensively, others may replace them with different communicative tools. This phenomenon is examined in depth through contrastive linguistic approaches. Research across languages and cultures shows that euphemisms are not only tied to language but are also deeply interconnected with social structures and mentalities. Existing studies emphasize the possibility of managing intercultural communication through *soft power* using euphemisms. Here, language functions not just as a medium, but as a strategic resource. From this perspective, studying the role of euphemisms in language policy, international relations, and social stability remains a relevant task for today's academic community.

Conclusion: From this standpoint, euphemisms serve as a vital tool at the social and pragmatic levels of language in intercultural communication. They not only soften the semantics of words and phrases but also play an essential role in preventing social discomforts, addressing cultural differences, and maintaining balance between communicators. Through their use in mass media and other communicative fields, euphemisms help preserve emotional stability and promote peace. Applying euphemisms as a communicative strategy in intercultural dialogue

requires further analysis in linguistics and cultural studies. This article considers it important to study euphemisms on linguistic, pragmatic, and cultural levels to facilitate effective intercultural communication.

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